

Study on Effect of Iron Deficiency Anemia on Level of HbA1c in Non-Diabetic Patients in Tertiary Care Hospital**Haresh Panchal¹, Harsh Patel², Sarita J Parmar³**¹Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, GMERS Medical College, Gandhinagar²Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, Ananya medical college, Kalol³Professor, Department of Medicine, Ananya Medical College, Kalol

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) is a type of haemoglobin that becomes glycosylated when the NH₂-terminal valine residue of the β -chain of globin is attached to a sugar molecule. It is a useful marker for determining a patient's blood sugar control during the past 3 months. However, there are several factors that might cause HbA1c levels to inaccurately appear lower or higher, regardless of actual blood sugar levels.

Aims and Objective: To assess the level of HbA1c in iron deficiency anemic non-diabetic patients compared to non-anemic non-diabetic healthy patients in tertiary care Hospital.

Material and Methods: Study participants were patients of iron deficiency anemia confirmed with laboratory test who were non-diabetic and another group of non-anemic non-diabetic healthy individuals who visited the Outpatient Department or were admitted in the ward in GMERS medical college, Gandhinagar and given informed consent to take part in study having age between 18 to 59 year and They were not be on any treatment like iron tablet or injection. Routine investigation CBC, S.Ferritin, S.iron, TIBC, Transferrin saturation and HbA1C, FBS, PPBS were done in each study participants.

Discussion: In the present study, a total of 200 participants were grouped into two groups – one group with 100 cases diagnosed with iron deficiency anemia and another group comprising of 100 healthy, non-anemic individuals age and gender matched to cases. There was statistically significant difference between the 2 groups with respect to RBC count, Hb, S.Iron, S. Ferritin, TIBC, Transferrin saturation, MCV, MCH and MCHC levels. HbA1C was significant higher in case group as compared to control.

Conclusion: In conclusion, iron deficiency anemia can have a considerable impact on the interpretation of HbA1c readings in individuals who do not have diabetes. It is possible for the total haemoglobin concentration is decreased as a result of insufficient iron levels, which can result in HbA1c values that are erroneously elevated.

Keyword: Iron deficiency anemia, HbA1C, Diabetes.

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Introduction

Haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) is a type of haemoglobin that becomes glycosylated when the NH₂-terminal valine residue of the β -chain of globin is attached to a sugar molecule. It is a useful marker for determining a patient's blood sugar control during the past 3 months. In recent years clinicians have been utilizing HbA1c as a method to identify and diagnose diabetes. HbA1c determination relies on three factors: (1) the level of HbA1c in reticulocytes upon their release from the bone marrow. (2) The rate at which HbA1c is synthesized (or the rate at which Hb is glycosylated) as red blood cells (RBCs) age, which is influenced by the concentration of glucose that Hb is exposed to; (3) the average age of RBCs in the bloodstream. HbA1c is commonly used as a marker for average blood sugar levels, a predictor of the likelihood of

diabetes-related problems, and an indicator of the effectiveness of diabetes management. However, there are several factors that might cause HbA1c levels to inaccurately appear lower or higher, regardless of actual blood sugar levels. These encompass structural haemoglobinopathies, thalassemia syndromes, and chemical modifications of haemoglobin. Furthermore, any factor that reduces the average age of red blood cells will inaccurately affect the findings of HbA1c tests, regardless of the specific technology employed for the assay. There has been little focus on the relationship between anemia and levels of HbA1c. Anemia like IDA can be linked to either increased erythrocyte turnover, resulting in decreased levels of Hb or decreased turnover or alterations in the three-dimensional structure of

haemoglobin (Hb), which can cause increased glycation of its N-terminal valine or consequently greater HbA1c levels.

Aims and Objectives: To assess the level of HbA1c in iron deficiency anemic nondiabetic patients compared to non-anemic non-diabetic healthy patients in tertiary care Hospital.

Material and Methods

Study Area: The present study was conducted in the Department of medicine in GMERS medical college, Gandhinagar, a tertiary care centre providing high quality and affordable healthcare services in the area.

Study duration: The duration of the present study was 1 year from Nov 2023 to Oct 2024

Study design: The present study was a comparative cross-sectional study.

Study Population: Study participants were patients of iron deficiency anemia who were non-diabetic and another group of non-anemic non-diabetic healthy individuals who visited the Outpatient Department or were admitted in the ward in GMERS medical college, Gandhinagar and given informed consent to take part in study fulfilling inclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with iron deficiency anemia with age between 18 to 59 year
- They should not be on any treatment like iron tablet or injection.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Age <18 years or >59 years
- Patients with diabetes / Impaired fasting glucose / Impaired glucose tolerance
- Patients with chronic renal failure / liver disease/ Thyroid/ metabolic disease

- Patients with other than Iron deficiency anemia
- Pregnancy, Chronic alcoholism
- Chronic blood loss, Known case of any malignancy.

According to the Demographic and Health Surveys program, (83)

- Mild Anemia-10.0-11.9g/dl
- Moderate Anemia-7.0-9.9 g/dl
- Severe Anemia –Less than 7.0g/dl

Methodology: After detailed history was taken, clinical examination was done patients were divided into 2 groups

Case Group: Confirmed case of iron deficiency anemia by lab test who were non-diabetic.

Control Group: Healthy non-anemic, non-diabetic controls.

All patients underwent the following investigations-CBC with reticulocyte count, Red blood cell morphology and RDW, Serum iron, serum ferritin, TIBC, Transferrin saturation, MCV, MCH and MCHC, HbA1c, FBS, PPBS, RFT, LFT, TFT

Data Management and Statistical Analysis: The collected data was entered and cleaned using MS-Excel and analysed statistically using Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 25. Anonymity of collected data was ensured. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean value \pm standard deviation (Mean \pm SD) or median \pm interquartile range (Median \pm IQR) depending upon the normality of the data. Qualitative data was expressed as percentages (%) or proportions. Appropriate statistical tests were used to infer association between two variables and a p value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of participants according to gender between two groups

Gender	Groups		t-statistic, p-value
	Case n (%)	Control n (%)	
Males	33 (33)	45 (45)	-1.17, 0.061
Females	67 (67)	55 (55)	
Total	100 (100)	100 (100)	

Table 2: comparison of participant according to age

Age	Groups		t-statistic, p-value
	Group A (case) n (%)	Group B (control) n (%)	
18 to 30 years	44 (44)	10 (10)	-4.70, 0.001
31 to 45 years	29 (29)	66 (66)	
46 to 59 years	27 (27)	24 (24)	
Total	100 (100)	100 (100)	

Table 3: Comparison of participants according to Haemoglobin

	Groups		t-statistic, p-value*
	Case (Mean \pm SD)	Control (Mean \pm SD)	
Haemoglobin (gm/dL)	7.88 \pm 2.28	13.23 \pm 0.78	-22.16, 0.001

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 4: Comparison of Red blood cell counts between study groups

	Group		t-statistic, p-value*
	Case (Mean \pm SD)	Control (Mean \pm SD)	
Red blood cell counts (millions per mm ³)	4.20 \pm 0.93	4.69 \pm 0.47	- 4.70, 0.01

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 5: Comparison of Serum iron between study groups

	Group		t-statistic, p-value*
	Case (Mean \pm SD)	Control (Mean \pm SD)	
Serum iron (μ g/dL)	28.01 \pm 17.63	108.09 \pm 26.69	-21.90, 0.001

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 6: Comparison of Serum ferritin between study groups

	Group		t-statistic, p-value*
	Case (Mean \pm SD)	Control (Mean \pm SD)	
Serum ferritin (ng/mL)	15.46 \pm 17.68	105.31 \pm 26.68	- 21.82, 0.001

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 7: Comparison of Total iron binding capacity between study groups

	Group		t-statistic, p-value*	p-
	Case (Mean \pm SD)	Control (Mean \pm SD)		
Total iron binding capacity (TIBC) (μ g/dL)	347.68 \pm 86.49	290.54 \pm 30.86	-6.22, 0.001	

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 8: Comparison of Transferrin saturation between study groups

	Group		t-statistic, p-value*
	Case (Mean \pm SD)	Control (Mean \pm SD)	
Transferrin saturation (%)	12.87 \pm 8.45	37.39 \pm 0.12	-19.72, 0.001

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 9: Comparison of blood indices between study groups

Blood indices	Group		t-statistic, p-value*
	Group A (Mean \pm SD)	Group B (Mean \pm SD)	
MCV (fL)	72.91 \pm 4.24	93.71 \pm 3.82	- 36.42, 0.001
MCH (pg/cell)	23.83 \pm 1.86	31.14 \pm 2.65	- 22.55, 0.001
MCHC (g/dL)	26.51 \pm 3.78	33.03 \pm 1.73	- 15.63, 0.001

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 10: Comparison of HbA1c between study groups

Parameter	Group		t-statistic, p-value*
	Group A (Mean \pm SD)	Group B (Mean \pm SD)	
HbA1c (%)	5.005 \pm 0.54	4.75 \pm 0.19	-4.45, 0.001

* P-value <0.05 statistically significant; Independent samples t-test applied

Table 10 show the comparison of HbA1c levels between study groups. The mean HbA1c levels were 5.005% in patients with iron deficiency anemia (group A) which was higher than the mean HbA1c levels in control group (4.75%). The difference between the two groups was statistically significant (p = 0.001).

Table 12: Comparison of HbA1c with Anemia and S.Iron level

Severity of Anemia	Levels of HbA1c	S.Iron Level
Mild (10.0–11.9 mg/dl)	4.29 ± 0.26	40.36 ± 6.49
Moderate (7.0-9.9 mg/dl)	4.93 ± 0.35	28.40 ± 9.24
Severe (<7 mg/dl)	5.61 ± 0.21	17.76 ± 5.84
p-value	0.001	0.001

As per this study severe anemic study group - Mean HbA1c level 5.61 and S.Iron level is 17.76. In Moderate anemic study group - Mean HbA1c level is 4.93 and S.Iron level is 28.4. In Mild anemic study group - Mean HbA1c level is 4.29 and S.Iron level is 40.36. All three groups have p value of <0.05 which is significant.

Discussion

In the present study, a total of 200 participants were grouped into two groups – one group with 100 cases diagnosed with iron deficiency anemia and another group comprising of 100 healthy, non-anemic individuals age and gender matched to cases. There was statistically significant difference between the 2 groups with respect to RBC count, Hb, Se. Iron, Se. Ferritin, TIBC, Transferrin saturation, MCV, MCH and MCHC levels. In our study severe anemic study group - Mean HbA1c level 5.61 and S.Iron level is 17.76. In Moderate anemic study group - Mean HbA1c level is 4.93 and S.Iron level is 28.4. In mild anemic study group – Mean HbA1c level is 4.29 and S.Iron level is 40.36. All three groups have p value of <0.05 which is significant. Overall mean level of HbA1c in case group is 5.005 and control group is 4.75. And its p value is <0.05 which is significant.

In another similar study by Reddy VT et al, among minimum 100 patients. It was found that, patients with iron deficiency anemia had a mean HbA1c of 5.86. The mean serum iron level in patients with HbA1c levels ranged from 4-5.6 was 24.25 (micromol/L). The corresponding mean serum iron for HbA1c range 5.7-6.4 was 22.25 (micromol/L). The corresponding mean serum iron for HbA1c levels greater than 6.5 was 21.96 (micromol/L). According to the findings, there is an inverse relationship between HbA1c and mean serum iron levels, and this relationship is statistically significant (p<0.05), i.e. mean serum iron decreases as HbA1c level increases. This finding is also similar to our present study.

In a more recent study in Indore, India by Sain V et al, a cross-sectional comparison study was carried out at the Index Medical College Hospital and Research Centre in Indore on non-diabetic patients based on fasting blood sugar of <100 mg/dl. There were two groups of patients. Patients with ID anemia were included in group-1, while healthy people who were age and sex matched but did not have ID were included in group-2. The ID groups mean HbA1c level was considerably higher

(5.88±0.43) than that of the non-ID group (5.51±0.48) so, our study have similar findings. Another cross-sectional study by Himanshu A et al, conducted on 200 non-diabetic subjects which were divided into group A (n=100, IDA but non-diabetic) and group B (n=100, normal healthy subjects without IDA and without diabetes). Mean Hb%, Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV), Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin (MCH), and Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin Concentration (MCHC), serum iron and ferritin were significantly higher in group B in comparison with group A (p-value <0.0001). Mean serum Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC) was significantly higher in group A subjects in comparison to group B. Mean HbA1c in group A was significantly on higher side as compared to group B. It showed that iron deficient patients had higher value of HbA1c as compared to non-iron deficient subjects. This study concluded that iron deficiency (decreased Hb%) leads to increase in HbA1c.

In a similar study among Saudi women by Bindayel IA et al, fifty-nine Saudi women (20 to 50 years old) were enrolled and categorized into groups according to their circulating haemoglobin concentration: Non-IDA (Hb ≥7.45 mmol/L; n= 38) and IDA (Hb ≤7.44 mmol/L; n= 21). The IDA group was further subdivided according to the severity of the IDA, as follows: mild (Hb 6.83 to 7.44 mmol/L; n=9) and moderate–severe (Hb <6.83 mol/L; n= 12). HbA1c, Hb, ferritin were measured in each participant. HbA1c did not significantly differ between the groups. This association was contradictory to our study and its showed study was non-significant.

Limitations

1. We cannot see effect of iron replacement therapy on the level of HbA1c in known case of iron deficiency anemia.
2. Sample Size could be a limitation which may have affected the generalizability of results.
3. Effect of physiological processes like pregnancy, lactation etc could have been included.
4. Further larger studies are required for ascertaining the findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, iron deficiency anemia can have a considerable impact on the interpretation of HbA1c readings in individuals who do not have diabetes. It is possible for the total haemoglobin concentration

is decreased as a result of insufficient iron levels, which can result in HbA1c values that are erroneously elevated.

The occurrence of this phenomenon highlights the significance of taking into account and researching the possibility of iron deficiency when evaluating glycemic control or diagnosing diabetes in patients who do not initially have diabetes. In the setting of iron deficiency anemia, clinicians should exercise caution and, where necessary, make use of additional diagnostic techniques in order to appropriately interpret the results of the HbA1c test.

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